

Competitive Intelligence and Productivity in Modern Age Academic Library: ICT Impact Assessment**Kikelomo Adeeko¹, (PhD)**adeeko308@gmail.com, adeekok@mcu.edu.ng

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^{1,2,4}McPherson University, Abeokuta, Nigeria.**DOI:** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10999410>**Abstract:**

The inability of the academic to cope with the vast output of new information and ever-increasing areas of human knowledge has placed a demand on the academic libraries to seek for modern strategies such as Competitive Intelligence and Information Communication Technology as a tool for increasing academic library productivity. This intelligence application of Information Communication Technology has changed academic libraries operations and performance. The study examines the influence of Competitive Intelligence and Information Communication Technology (ICT) in enhancing productivity in contemporary academic libraries. A descriptive survey research design was employed as the study guide. Eighty copies of a well design questionnaire were used to gather data from Librarians and Library Officers from the four selected university libraries. The questionnaire was analyzed using descriptive statistics. The study therefore reveals that training & retraining of staff on ICT, was the major way of improving academic library productivity through competitive intelligence use of ICT facilities followed by training & retraining of staff on competitive intelligence principles, provision of more ICT facilities, provision of regular power supply, sufficient allocation of funds to the academic library and formulation of policies that promote CI & ICT in academic libraries respectively.

Keywords: Competitive Intelligence, Productivity, Modern age, Information Communication Technology (ICT), Library Competitors.

Introduction

Global development in the world has greatly placed a high demand in every field of human endeavor to seek for more helpful ways of performing task to meet organizational objectives; seeking to improve productivity. The academic library is not exempted from this exercise, in fact, greater demand is placed on the academic library as an information custodian and provider to be proactive in this modern age of information explosion and overload to foster information dissemination for decision-making and research output. Competitive intelligence (CI) is one of the emerging ideas found relevant in improving productivity of any organizational system i.e. academic library inclusive.

Adegbite (2020) defines competitive intelligence (CI) as the capability to gather and use the information on factors that affect a company's competitive gain; organizations analyse collected data and information to grow active and effectual business practices, while Muritala & Ajetunmobi (2019) conceptualized CI as the application of official resources in expanding knowledge on rivalry, challengers and business community. Competitive intelligence as define by Ojo & Olaniyi (2017) is a process by which an organization legally gathers, analyzes, and strategically utilizes information related to its competitive environment. Competitive intelligence (CI) is the process of developing actionable foresight regarding competitive dynamics and non-market factors that can be used to enhance competitive advantage. Furthermore, 'competitive intelligence seeks to predict the future and on the basis of this, predicting strategic company decisions' (Barte, 2011).

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to investigate competitive intelligence and productivity in contemporary academic libraries. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Find out the areas of intelligence use of ICT in academic libraries.
- ii. Find out librarian/Academic Library Services competitors.
- iii. Determine ways of improving academic library productivity through competitive intelligence use of ICT facilities.
- iv. Determine the relationship between competitive intelligence and productivity of academic Libraries.

Research Questions

- i. What are the areas of intelligence use of ICT in academic libraries?
- ii. What are librarian/Academic Library Services competitors?
- iii. What are the ways of improving academic library productivity through competitive intelligence use of ICT facilities?

Research Hypothesis

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between Competitive intelligence and the productivity of academic Libraries.

Needs for Competitive Intelligence In Academic Libraries

Organization of information is an essential function of the academic library as well as the effective dissemination of information. Over the years, there have been different means of organizing information, with the vast output of new information and ever increasing areas of human knowledge to cope with by academic libraries, it is obvious that the use of traditional methods of acquisition, storage and dissemination of information will not permit the library to meet up with this great demand. It must be noted that the availability of information does not determine or guarantee success; rather it is the ability to turn information intelligence, which is the basic concept of competitive intelligence.

Similarly, Jerome, Nkiko, and Ifeakachuku (2017) highlighted that academic libraries are in a serious competition to contribute to their parent institution's competitive advantage and are faced with the challenges of rebranding their services over their competitors and remaining relevant as a hub of scholarship in this 21st-century business-driven environment. Furthermore, Akinola (2021) opined that the competitive intelligence process help firms (academic library inclusive) to obtain, process, analyze, spread, and interpret competitor's information vigorously and systematically, in order to respond appropriately. Hilterbrand (2010) also identify three main steps in the competitive use of information as the gathering of information, extracting information, and applying context to information.

Examining the above statement, it can be deduced that the application of CI concept in an academic library will make a great impact on data and information gathering, analyses, and dissemination for decision-making by researchers, policy makers, and planners. CI could be used as a tool to alert the management of the

library of both threats and opportunities, a means to deliver reasonable assessment, and take proper action as a means of increasing academic library productivity.

Conceptual Clarification

Gračanin, Kalac & Jovanović (2015) in their study on CI importance and application in practice submitted that it is recent that companies now realize that the application of CI helps to understand how and where to find unique resources and capabilities as well as estimate unique ways of combining its resources for creating values for its customers; which can improve their position on the market. They further emphasized that the use of CI prevents the erosion of information and skills. This is also supported by Kumar Subramanian, Standholm (2001) who identified that CI created comparative knowledge that enables companies to highlight their strength. Gračanin et al. further maintained that the key which helps to designing a successful strategy is the ability to identify, develop and maintain a competitive edge over rivals.

In an exploratory study by Abolarinwa & Yaya (2015) on the utilization of competitive intelligence by health information workers (i.e. Library personnel) of the Nigerian Institute of Medical Research (NMIR) submitted that competitive intelligence in library service is considered a very important requirement for efficient and effective service delivery in a library; because a library is an essential element in the educational and research endeavor of the research institute. The paper therefore, recommended that more attention should be given to the utilization of competitive intelligence in library services and that health information workers should make the best use of their competitive intelligence to plan service provision, promote the available services, and deliver them efficiently and effectively. Muritala, Asikhia, Makinde & Akinlabi (2019) survey research examined competitive intelligence and employee productivity of selected insurance firms in Nigeria and found that competitive intelligence had a positive relationship with employee productivity. The study recommends that managers should put in place good programs to provide employees with the right attitudes, knowledge, communication skills, and authority to handle non-routine transactions.

Similarly, Achonna, Osisanwo and Yaya, (2014) discussed competitive intelligence as a tool for effective job performance in the academic library. The paper found that there is a need to identify and use a variety of non-traditional information sources such as competitive intelligence that would enable the academic library to edge out its competitors and make library users to develop a renewed interest in the services provided by the library in meeting their information needs. While, Anyawn & Nwosu (2016) in their study

emphasis that productivity enhancement is the extent to which the use of ICT facilities promotes library operations & sources.

Academic Library Productivity

Globally, organisations strive to improve and sustain productivity due to its profound impact as it leads to more income, more patronage and a high growth rate (Oyeboade & Olajojo; 2016). *Chris Hare and Gary Geer, (Productivity Paradox ALA1997) conceptualized productivity as an economic measure consisting of input (investment) and output (profit). Thus a company that most minimizes input and maximizes output has the highest productivity and this refers to the general efficiency of an organization or individual.*

Yaya, Akintayo, and Uzohue (2016) conceptualized productivity as the ability to produce an item or service in the organization. Also, scholars see it as efforts that an individual employee exerts towards the general production of goods and services of the organization with the least input of labour, material, and machines. Ogunsanwo (2012) defined productivity as the rate at which a worker, an organization, or a country produces goods and services.

In Nigerian public university libraries, librarians' productivity entails providing relevant educational resources in the library that would encourage innovative research works in the university (Yaya, Akintayo&Uzohue; 2016). In the same vein, Association of College and Research Libraries -- ACRL (2006) stressed that libraries and librarians are fulcrums of academic productivity, with the potential to expand both the range and depth of creative work that faculty and students undertake in any discipline.

Therefore to survive and compete successfully in today's changing environment, organisations like academic libraries require employees to be proactive, show initiative while engaging with their role, and remain committed to performing at high standards. Academic libraries as Organizational must seek for ways of improving its efficiency by engaging CI Process of using fewer resources and time to achieve the same goal as well as strategize to outsmart competitors.

Similarly, for an academic library to be on top of competitors and gain more customers it must deliberately and constantly acquire quality and quantity information resources that will attract and add value to service users (Jerome, Nkiko & Ifeakachuku; 2017).

Competitive Intelligence Five Phases

Paula (2017) enumerated the following five (5) phases as CI circle

- ❖ Planning of Resources and activities: For effective delivery of services, there is a need for proper planning. Itemizing the steps to take for proper decision, definitely, this can only be achieved with adequate information.
- ❖ Collection and Validation of information: The above will lead to the collection of data/information gathering and validation of the gathered information. Validation of data is necessary to determine the relevance and usability of the collected data.
- ❖ Analysis and dissemination of Intelligence: This involves intelligence analysis of the task to be carried out with the collected data, as well as dissemination of intelligence information.
- ❖ Using the results: The information disseminated will be used by the organisation to improve productivity
- ❖ Evaluation of process: It is essential for the whole system/process to be evaluated for further improvement and adjustment where necessary in an organisational system. This will also help to determine the level of achievement and the number of recorded successes.

Competitive intelligence cycle

Academic Library Productivity, Competitive Intelligence and ICT

Advancement in Information Communication Technology (ICT) has brought tremendous changes to the way information is processed and stored in modern academic libraries.

Kumar and Kaur (2005) submitted that the current information revolution and the increasing impact of Information Communication Technology has modernized the process of learning and research in most universities. Manjunatha (2009) supporting the view stated that technological advancement have made a significant impact on the growth of knowledge and unlocking of human potential in the library which is clearly visible on information resources, services and people. He explained that the effective use of information technology (IT) in Libraries increases efficiency in operations, eliminates the repetitive nature of work, and improves the quality and range of services.

Ojo and Olaniyi (2017) opined that competitive intelligence as a tool is made possible because of the availability and accessibility of information as well as information products and services which library and information professionals are trained to provide. Fagbe, Amanze and Oladipupo (2015) described ICT in the library to be concerned with the acquisition, processing, storage, and dissemination of information, textual, numerical, pictorial, and vocal. While Ayo (2001) sees ICT as the use of computer systems and telecommunications equipment in information handling through electronic processing using the computer, the transmission of information using telecommunication equipment, and dissemination of information multimedia. Mishra and Mishra (2014) Mishra and Mishra (2014) asserted that access has replaced ownership and the Internet has made remote access to databases possible 24 hours 7 days per week. Thus university library finds itself in a time of tremendous challenge which is also a time of boundless opportunity to use ICT creatively to enhance service delivery to the user.

Thus, with the above-highlighted features of ICT in handling information it could be clearly stated that its intelligent use by the librarian in an academic library to meet the needs of its customers (library users) will help the library to maintain its position in information processing and helps in sustaining the interest of the user. Similarly, the application of the principles of competitive intelligence in an academic library with the use of ICT facilities will definitely enhance librarian productivity and bring about more innovations in the basic/general library services such as: Lending /circulating services, Inter-library loan (ILL) & Document delivery, Reference service, Reservation, Current awareness, Exhibition and Display, Library publications

user education, Information literacy programme, Literature search, Selective dissemination, Compilation of bibliographies and indexes reprographic services.

This use of ICT to perform all the in-house operations like acquisition processing, circulations, maintenance, and serial management is called library automation. The need for automation arises to reduce the effort required for these jobs. Gulam and Ashok (2011) opined that competitive Intelligence will help the library management to decide on the library software package to be used for the library automation. It is obvious that many software is available in the market for library automation but not all are efficiently meeting the task facing the librarian in this age. The librarian will have to intelligently consider the task to be performed by the software, the cost, its efficient performance in any institution using it, and the mode of applying it so as to meet the parent institution's goals.

The huge storage devices such as CD-ROMs, DVDs, and memory cards that came to existence through ICT are a great advantage in information collection storage, analyses, and dissemination, without loss of value or content. The intelligent use of ICT has changed the academic library from a building housing book to a database for universal access to information. The academic library could keep huge volumes of information database CDs over a long period of time without the image on quality degradation while saving space and thus increasing user's satisfaction. The internet which has now turned the world into a global village has given the academic library the privilege of providing universal access of information, while digital libraries which occupies little space. Enhance library networking and resource sharing. This has expanded the limitation of the scope of resource sharing and information exchange. (Mishra & Mishra; 2014).

The modern academic library now have access to online full-text databases, e-journals, e-books, and library catalogue of other institutions which have been intelligently filtered and archived based on the parent institution's needs and likely research areas of student. Thus, library users need not seek for junks of information since they are already carefully selected journals for the user in the library. All of the above are indicators of academic libraries' productivity.

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was employed as the study guide. A well designed questionnaire was used to gather data for the study. Seventy copies of questionnaires were returned out of 80 questionnaires distributed. Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation

to describe variables and their occurrences. The hypothesis was tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (**PPMC**) to consolidate the research question(s) highlighted earlier. Tables were also used in the presentation and analysis of the data. The data were analysed based on the research questions. The collected demographic data from the respondents and their responses were likewise presented and analysed using simple percentage and frequency distribution methods.

Scope of the Study

The study is limited to four universities in South-West, Nigeria: (two public universities and two private universities) that were purposively selected. They include the University of Ibadan, the Federal University of Agriculture Abeokuta, Lead City University, and McPherson University. The study population includes professional and Para-professional Librarians of the above stated universities libraries.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the respondents

Variable	Labels	Frequency	Percentage
University	LEAD City University	14	20.0
	McPherson University	8	11.4
	University of Ibadan	26	37.1
	FUNAAB	22	31.4
Gender	Male	34	48.6
	Female	36	51.4
Age	21-25 years	6	8.6
	26-30 years	7	10.0
	31-35 years	12	17.1
	36-40 years	8	11.4

	41-45 years	12	17.1
	46-50 years	16	22.9
	51 years and above	9	12.9
Marital status	Single	13	18.6
	Married	54	77.1
	Divorced	3	4.3
Academic qualification	ND/NCE	8	11.4
	HND	5	7.1
	Bachelor's Degree	18	25.7
	Master's Degree	25	35.7
	Ph.D	10	14.3
	Others	4	5.7
Status/Designation	Library officer	25	35.7
	Librarian II	11	15.7
	Librarian I	11	15.7
	Senior Librarian	12	17.1
	Principal Librarian	8	11.4
	Other	3	4.3
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	Principal Librarian	8	11.4
	Other	3	4.3

Table 1 above showed that 14(20.0%) of the respondents were from LEAD City University, 8(11.4%) were from McPherson University, 26(37.1%) from the University of Ibadan and 22(31.4%) from FUNAAB. 34(48.6%) were males while 36(51.4%) were females. 6(8.6%) were aged 21-25 years, 7(10.0%) were aged 26-30 years, 12(17.1%) were aged 31-35 years, 8(11.4%) were aged 36-40 years, 12(17.1%) were aged 41-45 years, 16(22.9%) were aged 46-50 years and 9(12.9%) were aged 51 years and above. 13(18.6%) were Single, 54(77.1%) were Married and 3(4.3%) were Divorced. 8(11.4%) had ND/NCE certificate, 5(7.1%) had HND certificate, 18(25.7%) had Bachelor's Degree certificate, 25(35.7%) had Master's Degree certificate, 10(14.3%) had Ph.D certificate and 4(5.7%) had Other certificates. 25(35.7%) were Library officers, 11(15.7%) were Librarian II, 11(15.7%) were Librarian I, 12(17.1%) were Senior Librarian, 8(11.4%) were Principal Librarian and 3(4.3%) belonged to other Status.

Research Questions:

RQ1: What are the areas of intelligence use of ICT in academic libraries?

Table 2: Areas of intelligence use of ICT in academic libraries

s/n	Areas	SD	D	A	SA	\bar{x}	S.D
1	Reference service	2		22	46	3.60	.65
		2.9%	%	31.4%	65.7%		

2	Catalogue & Classification	3	23	44	3.59	.58
	%	4.3%	32.9%	62.9%		
3	Indexing	1	37	32	3.44	.53
	%	1.4%	52.9%	45.7%		
4	Users education	7	26	37	3.43	.67
	%	10.0%	37.1%	52.9%		
5	Selective dissemination of information	1	5	27	3.43	.69
	1.4%	7.1%	38.6%	52.9%		
6	E-journals	1	6	25	3.43	.71
	1.4%	8.6%	35.7%	54.3%		
7	OPAC	1	6	27	3.40	.71
	1.4%	8.6%	38.6%	51.4%		
8	Electronic Books	9	24	37	3.40	.71
	%	12.9%	34.3%	52.9%		
9	Publishing	3	5	31	3.29	.78
	4.3%	7.1%	44.3%	44.3%		
10	Document Delivery	4	2	38	3.23	.76
	5.7%	2.9%	54.3%	37.1%		
11	Inter library loan	6	2	33	3.21	.87
	8.6%	2.9%	47.1%	41.4%		

12	Preservation	2	7	36	25	3.20	.73
		2.9%	10.0%	51.4%	35.7%		
13	Bibliographies	7	3	33	27	3.14	.91
		10.0%	4.3%	47.1%	38.6%		

Weighted \bar{x} = 3.37

Responses on the areas of intelligence use of ICT in academic libraries are as shown below:

Reference service(\bar{x} =3.60) was the major area of intelligence use of ICT in academic libraries and was followed by Cataloguing & Classification(\bar{x} =3.59), Indexing(\bar{x} =3.44), Users education(\bar{x} =3.43), Selective dissemination of information(\bar{x} =3.43), E-journals(\bar{x} =3.43), OPAC(\bar{x} =3.40), Electronic Books(\bar{x} =3.40), Publishing (\bar{x} =3.29), Document Delivery (\bar{x} =3.23), Interlibrary loan (\bar{x} =3.21), Preservation (\bar{x} =3.20) and Bibliographies (\bar{x} =3.14) respectively.

RQ2: What are librarian/Academic Library Services competitors?

Table 3: Rating of librarian/Academic Library Services competitors

s/n	Items	SD	D	A	SA	\bar{x}	S.D
1	e-book providers	2	7	35	26	3.21	.74
		2.9%	10.0%	50.0%	37.1%		
2	Website providers	2	10	33	25	3.16	.77
		2.9%	14.3%	47.1%	35.7%		
3	Internet providers	3	12	32	23	3.07	.82
		4.3%	17.1%	45.7%	32.9%		
4	Online vendors	3	12	37	18	3.00	.78

		4.3%	17.1%	52.9%	25.7%		
5	Special/private information centers	3	14	34	19	2.99	.81
		4.3%	20.0%	48.6%	27.1%		
6	Telecommunication operators	7	17	20	26	2.93	1.01
		10.0%	24.3%	28.6%	37.1%		

Weighted $\bar{x} = 3.06$

Table 3 presents information on the level at which the above media competes with Librarian/Academic Library Services. It showed that majority of the librarians indicated “e-book providers” (Disagreed = 9(12.9%), Agreed = 61(87.1%), $\bar{x} = 3.21$), “Website providers” (Disagreed = 12(17.2%), Agreed = 58(82.8%), $\bar{x} = 3.16$), “Internet providers” (Disagreed = 15(21.4%), Agreed = 55(78.6%), $\bar{x} = 3.07$), “Online vendors” (Disagreed = 15(21.4%), Agreed = 55(78.6%), $\bar{x} = 3.00$), “Special/private information centers” (Disagreed = 17(24.3%), Agreed = 53(75.7%), $\bar{x} = 2.99$) and “Telecommunication operators” (Disagreed = 24(34.3%), Agreed = 46(65.7%), $\bar{x} = 2.93$).

Inference to be drawn from the above result is that most librarians agreed that librarian/Academic Library Services were highly competed with by the following media, e-book providers, Website providers, Internet providers, Online vendors, Special/private information centres and Telecommunication operators respectively. Thus, most of the librarian are aware of librarian/Academic Library Services competitors.

Table 4: Test of norm showing the level at which the above stated media competes with Librarian/Academic Library Services

Maximum score = 24 Interval = $\frac{24}{2} = 12$, Classification = High, Low

Interval	Range	Level Competition	Frequency (%)
1-12		Low	6(8.6%)
13-24	18.36	High	64(91.4%)

Going by the test of norm result, it can be deduced that the level at which these media competes with Librarian/Academic Library Services is high.

RQ3: What are the ways of improving academic library productivity through competitive intelligence use of ICT facilities?

Table 5: ways of improving academic library productivity through competitive intelligence use of ICT facilities

s/n	Ways of improving academic library productivity	SD	D	A	SA	\bar{x}	S.D
1	Training & retraining of staff on ICT	-	2	22	46	3.63	.54
			2.9%	31.4%	65.7%		
2	Training & retraining of staff on competitive intelligence principles	2	3	17	48	3.59	.71
		2.9%	4.3%	24.3%	68.6%		
3	Provision of more ICT facilities	-	4	22	44	3.57	.60
			5.7%	31.4%	62.9%		
4	Provision of regular power supply	-	3	25	42	3.56	.58
			4.3%	35.7%	60.0%		
5	Sufficient allocation of funds to academic library	1	4	26	39	3.47	.68
		1.4%	5.7%	37.1%	55.7%		
6	Formulation of policies that promote CI & ICT in academic libraries	-	5	27	38	3.47	.63
			7.1%	38.6%	54.3%		
Weighted \bar{x} = 3.55							

Responses on the ways of improving academic library productivity through competitive intelligence use of ICT facilities are as shown below:

Training & retraining of staff on ICT ($\bar{x}=3.63$), was the major way of improving academic library productivity through competitive intelligence use of ICT facilities followed by Training & retraining of staff on competitive intelligence principles ($\bar{x}=3.59$), Provision of more ICT facilities ($\bar{x}=3.57$), Provision of regular power supply ($\bar{x}=3.56$), Sufficient allocation of funds to the academic library ($\bar{x}=3.47$) and Formulation of policies that promote CI & ICT in academic libraries ($\bar{x}=3.47$) respectively.

Test of Hypothesis:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between Competitive intelligence and Library productivity of Librarians in academic libraries.

Table 6: PPMC showing the relationship between Competitive intelligence and Library productivity

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	N	r	p-value	Remark
Competitive intelligence	18.371	4.0862	70	.250*	.037	Sig.
Library productivity	21.2857	2.8034				

* Sig at 0.05 levels

Table 6 above showed that there was a positive significant relationship between Competitive intelligence and the Library productivity of Librarians ($r = .250^*$, $N= 70$, $p <.05$).

Hence, Competitive intelligence had a positive influence on Library productivity among Librarians of academic libraries in the study.

The null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

This study reveals that reference service was the major area of intelligence use of ICT in academic libraries and was followed by Cataloguing& Classification, Indexing, Users education, Selective dissemination of

information, E-journals, OPAC, Electronic Books, Publishing, Document Delivery, Interlibrary loan, Preservation, and Bibliographies, respectively.

Furthermore, the result shows that majority of the librarians agreed and are aware that Librarian/Academic Library Services were highly competed with by the following media, e-book providers, Website providers, Internet providers, Online vendors, Special/private information centres and Telecommunication operators respectively. Librarian are aware of library competitors and the level going by the test of norm result, indicate that the level at which these media competes with Librarian/Academic Library Services is high. This is in agreement with the submission of Yayaet. al,,(2014) that in Nigeria today, academic libraries were having some organizations that are competing with their services and that if urgent steps were not taken these organizations may send librarians out of their laudable profession, they organisations include: i.) Internet and web sites providers ii.) Telecommunication (telephone) operators, and other Online vendors, Archives and documentation centres.

Therefore, the necessity is laid on academic library to explore the opportunity and seek for information among their counterparts to improve the library services and thereby provide quality information materials to meet the needs of patrons (Diyalou, 2019). Haliso and Aina (2012) similarly submitted that competitive approach in libraries is the ability to seek information from other counterpart's libraries and make use of the information to provide quality services and be in a better position than others.

This study further reveals that training & retraining of staff on ICT was the major way of improving academic library productivity through competitive intelligence use of ICT facilities followed by Training & retraining of staff on competitive intelligence principles, Provision of more ICT facilities, Provision of regular power supply, Sufficient allocation of funds to academic library and Formulation of policies that promote CI & ICT in academic libraries respectively. Competitive intelligence had a positive influence on Library productivity among Librarians of academic libraries in the study. The finding is in consonance with the finding of Waithaka (2016); Muritala, Asikhia, Makinde & Akinlabi (2019) which indicate that competitive intelligence practices have a positive, and significant relationship with employee productivity. While, Jerome, Nkiko, & Ifeakachuku (2017) study submitted that if Libraries must compete effectively in this 21st century environment they must take advantage of technologies to disseminate information to users so as to have an edge over their competitors.

Uzohue & Yaya (2016) Opined that the internet is the most important means of producing raw data into actionable intelligence and has also provided a lot of resources for competitive advantages therefore, improved information flow can improve the quality of decision making and internal operations. Likewise as a competitive intelligence source, the Internet is both an additional source of information and a cost-effective means of sharing and disseminating information for decision makers (Gračanin, Kalac & Jovanović; 2015).

Similarly, academic libraries must ensure the accessibility of intelligence information to library users. Library collection must be well filtered to make a difference, because a lot of information providers such as website providers, online vendors, and telecommunications operators are trying to compete with the academic library in providing information to the academic community i.e. lecturers, students, etc, the academic library must make distinct efforts in retaining its position by providing intelligent information. The libraries must assert their evolving roles in more active ways, both in the context of their institutions and in the increasingly competitive markets for information dissemination and retrieval (Adewusi; 2021).

Conclusion

Academic libraries play a vital role in the achievement/realization of effective teaching and research work as well as the development of any academic community through the intellectual gathering of information, the transmission of knowledge to intelligence, and providing access to different sources of knowledge for decision-making.

Competitive Intelligence and Information Communication tools have supported library functions such as: circulation, serials, acquisition control, cataloguing as well as other routine library services. Competitive Intelligence will not only provides knowledge but will filter information which is essential in this information evolution age. The use of ICT will promote the performance of the academic library. Anyanwu & Nwosu (2016) opined that with the use of ICT facilities, a functioning academic library system characterised as a harmonious and interactive union of people, materials, and technology has emerged. They further submitted that lack of infrastructure to provide access to electronic information or erratic power supply; lack of ICT facilities will make academic libraries to find their job tasking and consequently jeopardise productivity enhancement.

Recommendations

The extent to which CI & ICT facilities are used in enhancing productivity; thus there is a need for all academic libraries to embrace the use of Competitive Intelligence principles and Information Communication Technological tools to aid information processing and transmission work which the library is known for to enhance proper decision making.

Library management should organise training, to focus on competitive intelligence as well as expose staff to ICT techniques and its application in the library.

Parent institutions and government should provide adequate funds for the academic library to meet up with the financial demand involved in carrying on with the new technological explosion of this age.

Librarians in the academic library should be willing and get themselves prepared knowing fully well that we are in the age of competitive activities so as to retain their position.

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